

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

BriFace

H2020:MSCA-IF-2018

Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring method

(H2020-MSCA-IF-2018 Marie Skłodowska-Curie)

Fellow: Dr D. Achillopoulou

Coordinator: Dr S Mitoulis | **Academic Advisor:** Dr Y Wang

Industrial partners & Stakeholders: Sika A.G., Denco Structural Eng. P.C.

Duration: 24 months (start date: June 2019) | Overall budget: € 212 933,76

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223811/factsheet/en>

Grant agreement ID: 845549

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

Author: Dr Dimitra V Achillopoulou

1. Assessment methods-technical solutions.
2. Description of the monitoring techniques.
3. Examples of the strengthening measures for bridge decks.
4. Appendix A

Copyright information:

The above plan creator(s) have agreed that others may use as much of the text of this plan as they would like in their own plans, and customise it as necessary. You do not need to credit the creator(s) as the source of the language used, but using any of the plan's text does not imply that the creator(s) endorse, or have any relationship to, your project or proposal.

This document has been prepared for the European Commission however it reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Last modified:

v2: 07/2021

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

1. Assessment methods:

A strengthening strategy starts by assessing the existing condition. The condition assessment of an existing RC bridge aims at determining whether the bridge will function safely over a specified residual service life. Guidelines for assessment of existing bridges have been developed in many countries. They are commonly separated in phases, starting with a preliminary evaluation, followed by a detailed investigation, expert investigation, and finally an advanced assessment, depending on the structural condition of the investigated bridge [1] and back analysis for calculating the resistance. The main categories of the assessment procedure are [2], [3], [4], [5]:

- i) Visual inspection (VI),
- ii) Load testing response (LTR),
- iii) Finite element modelling (FEM),
- iv) Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE),
- v) Structural Health Monitoring (SHM).

2. Description of the monitoring techniques: Structural Health and Functionality Monitoring (SHFM) of transport infrastructure: methods and technologies.

2.1 Sensing technologies for SHFM

This section includes a description of traditional and advanced sensing methods for monitoring infrastructure assets and networks, such as highways, railways and transport hubs. A systematic literature overview was conducted based on: i) relevant keywords (e.g. monitoring, transport, infrastructure, NDTs, sensors, airborne, terrestrial), ii) publications mainly published over the last five years, iii) peer-reviewed scientific papers highly cited and reports from important research projects and initiatives, including standardisation committees. The review is summarised in Tables A.1 & A.2 (see Appendix A), in which the main techniques are classified [6], [7], based on the function principle [8], [9], [10] and the measurands [11], as well as the usefulness in assessing risk and measuring resilience [12], their advantages and disadvantages or limitations in application. **Table A.1 in Annex A** summarises the most important NDTs and also discusses whether instrumentation is required, or measurements can be taken remotely or contactless. **Table A.2** summarises the advantages and disadvantages of the methods, and their cost i.e. low, moderate, high, as an estimation of the resources and equipment required, and their practicality in risk and resilience assessments.

The owners, operators and stakeholders, who manage infrastructure, are responsible for the collection, interpenetration and secure retention of monitoring data. Based on these archived data, the structural integrity is documented and reports on the safety evaluation of the asset and the functionality of the network are assembled. The documentation includes evidence from the frequent inspections in structural and non-structural members [4]. The most common SHFM method is the conventional visual inspection [13], [14],[6] of infrastructure and networks, which is historically the most traditional and direct engineering method. This has always been raising the question of defining the suitable frequency in which inspections are conducted or how to inspect non-accessible members or long-distant members, e.g. foundations, pipelines, rebars. This approach enables a lot of subjectivism and uncertainty, as it is predominantly based on visual examination, experience and engineering judgement. Moreover, except for the practical difficulty of accessing hidden parts, assets present minute cracking, which is not always detectable visually or by applying simple inspection equipment, usually used in practice, such as magnifiers. These cracks might be proven important to the global performance of the asset and its detection is not possible visually, but only when its impact is disastrous for the operation of the infrastructure (e.g. fatigue cracks, propagated corrosion). Monitoring methods, including non-destructive testing (NDTs) are very popular in transport infrastructure because they are less invasive to the critical members and provide numerous measurands (see Appendix A, Tables A.1&2).

The ongoing digital revolution and advanced material science have introduced significant innovation and have completely reformed monitoring techniques. Starting from the times of the simple visual inspections, the evolution of sensing technology and miniaturization of sensors and novel non-destructive testing, as well as the enhanced computer power, has offered many options for recording diverse measurands. All these techniques, listed in the tables of Appendix A, add value to the damage detection and provide feedback for the health and functionality in an expedient and objective manner. Monitoring techniques can be (see Appendix A: Table A.1) contactless (C), distant (D), wireless (WL), instrumented (I), autonomous (AU), unattended (U), aerial (A), terrestrial (T). Lately, a lot of attention has been given to the remote, wireless sensing, smart and digital means of recording of vast information and big data, in almost real-time. More specifically, unmanned aerial technology, e.g. drones, helicopters, has been extensively used. A drone-enhanced inspection enables access to areas that may pose health, safety and environmental risks in an expedient manner. The drone inspection is the preferred method for visual surveys across a wide range of transport infrastructure applications as it is safe and accurate [15], [2]. Equally, traffic cameras and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV/Drones) are promising systems in asset management of transport networks [16], which can provide both qualitative and quantitative data. There is a number of research projects studying further the development of novel and advanced, digital, unmanned, automated monitoring devices, e.g. scanning cars, e.g. Trimis, Smart Structures, Sustainable Bridges, Smart Structures, Memscan, Isms, Wi-Health, Cross-It, Bridgemon, Rpb Healtec, Senskin, Cobri, Aerobi [17].

2.2 SHFM data analysis methods

Both physics-based and data-driven methods are developed and combined to visualise the damages on infrastructure. In the cases of transport infrastructure, the exposure conditions, the failure patterns, and the consequent traffic disruptions [18] are crucial parameters that enable the quantification of the remaining capacity of structural members as well as defining risks. In practice, a combination of monitoring systems is applied especially in landmark and/or critical infrastructure [19], [20]. Physics-based methods provide accurate results regarding the visualisation of the crack patterns or changes in geometry or at the mechanical properties of materials [21], [22], for example, Digital Image Correlation method. Further characterisation requires, in most cases, further documentation and tests for result validation, that is, semi/non-destructive testing (NDT). The characterisation of damages often is challenging. For example, if wave propagation and ultrasonic methods are used for detecting, mapping and characterising damages within assets, the interpretation of the scattering field or the decomposition of the wave modes in time or frequency domain is time-consuming and complex [23], [24], [25],[26], [27], [28], [29], [30]. This means that further processing if needed based on the geometry and the mechanical properties of the asset or the interoperabilities of the network.

Monitoring requirements tend to increase nowadays, and there are cases of technologically advanced countries e.g. Japan, where real-time continuous data have been recorded for many years, see the cases of the Yokohama Bay, Rainbow or Tsurumi Fairway Bridge, Hollandse Brug [31], [32], [34]. The so-called data-driven methods aim at streamlining the big data obtained with the interpretation of results, especially if the objective is to expediently quantify the resilience of critical infrastructure by using SHFM systems [33].

2.3 Physics-based methods for monitoring-enhanced resilience quantification

Transport infrastructure management relies heavily on the continuous feedback from SHFM systems for the assessment and prognosis of the capacity of the assets and the functionality of the networks [35]. This process includes the diagnosis of the damages to allocate resources on disaster mitigation and recovery actions. For the design, assessment and prediction of performance, currently, there are models available for simulating assets and networks. The validation of these models is typically achieved by comparing SHFM measured data with the engineered predictions' values (model). The latter explains the benefit of monitoring, which essentially provides valuable and accurate input data of monitored

infrastructure assets, which are then used in model updating [36]. Continuous SHFM feedback can potentially provide evidence of asset and infrastructure responses and hence means of evaluating capacity and functionality for normal and emergency circumstances, e.g. after natural disasters, which is useful for accurate and rapid quantification of risk and recovery. The output of this procedure, known as model updating, is practically the procedure to obtain an accurate representation of the structural condition and functionality of the asset in real-time [37], toward resilience-based infrastructure management.

2.3.1 Model updating

Model updating is described to emphasize the importance of reducing the uncertainties of prediction models based on monitoring data with various sensitivities. It aims at finding the best match of numerically derived parameters with the ones obtained from the monitoring systems (SHFM), by changing iteratively physical parameters in the numerical model, using an optimisation algorithm. It is a typical inverse dynamic problem, which was used to calibrate and/or verify the numerical model [38]. In recent years, model updating has been used to identify structural damages, based on the data from SHM systems [39], [40]. The methodology can be realised in two steps. Initially, the numerical model, for instance, a finite element model (FEM), can be updated based on the structural data in a healthy or as-designed state. This is the calibration step, which ensures that the model can produce output with very similar, if not the same, responses as the actual structure under the same actions. In the second step, the calibrated numerical model is updated based on actual, SHFM-based, structural responses whilst being in the damaged state. This is the identification step that leads to structural damage detection, localisation, characterization and quantification.

The inverse problem is essentially an optimisation process, i.e. algorithm, which is controlled by three key factors. First, the input variables, which are to be optimised, should be selected and be bounded by some prescribed ranges, which are determined according to the degree of uncertainty that governs the input parameters. Second, the comparison of measured data and prediction results in a set of equations that need to be combined to obtain the updated output (Figure 1). This is the so-called objective function (OF), which should be mathematically well-defined as described in [41] Third, the optimisation should be carefully selected. Numerous efforts have been made based on vibration responses. Traditionally, modal parameters, such as natural frequencies, mode shapes, and their derivatives, have been widely used as the objective function. More recently, model updating has been realised based on responses measured by various non-destructive testing (NDT), e.g. vibrations, strains, displacements [42], [43], [44]. Civil infrastructure systems are normally very complex, and thus their numerical models contain a large number of variables [45]. This large number of input variables creates, in most cases, complexity for the mathematical solution, since far more variables exist than the equations derived of the objective function, resulting in an undetermined problem. Thus, there is a range of solutions concerning the input for the infrastructure model, which can match the real asset. As such, the reduction of the variables is essential in defining a determined problem with a unique solution. The reduction of the number of variables is achieved with different methods e.g. sensitivity analysis [46], substructure method [47] and damage function method [39]. After the establishment of the optimisation, the solution remains challenging, because the objective function (OF) is usually nonlinear [39]. Hence, the relationship between the results of the asset model and the actual structure is not linear. Many reasons contribute, among which the changes of the exposure of the structure in environmental conditions, change of ecosystem, the material response over time, undetected cumulative damages and construction imperfections (absorption period). The solution of the inverse problem is a time-consuming and tedious mathematical task. As a result, selecting a powerful optimisation algorithm is an important task. There are numerous algorithms for optimisation, including traditional ones e.g. gradient-based [48] and intelligent ones [49]. For example, the Estimation of Distribution Algorithm (EDA) is an efficient one [50], as it can provide both the updated parameters and the distributions of the updated parameters.

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

Data-driven models, such as the SHMnet [51], can be part of the updating as well (deep-learning). The FEM that represents the asset is typically used for the prediction of its performance, but they can be substituted by reduced-order models that parametrise the physical properties. These methods are helpful in the identification and quantification of damages [36]. As such, model updating has the potential to become a general principle in the SHFM field especially since accuracy is guaranteed and enable the quantification of the risk and resilience.

Figure 1: Optimisation algorithm for model updating

3. Examples of the strengthening measures for bridge decks

The industrial partner of the Briface project has shared information about the strengthening of landmark bridges world-widely. This section includes 10 bridges strengthened with various systems of composite materials [52]:

1. A3 Escher Canal Bridge, Glarus (Switzerland) Project.

The three-span bridge on the A3 Sargans Zürich motorway, built in 1957, crosses the Escher Canal near Weesen (Figure 2a). The structure is a fully prestressed box girder type. It met a problem during an inspection in 1964, that was a crack running the whole length of the bridge was found in the centre of the underside of the deck. This was then continuously monitored until mitigation measures were decided. Deck slab was strengthened transversely for positive and negative moments with Sika® CarboDur® CFRP plates. The tensioned plates on the underside of the deck slab act as external prestressing (Figure 2b). The tensioning force is transferred to the concrete only at the ends of the plates and these were carefully located to achieve the maximum strengthening effect.

Figure 2. A3 Escher Canal Bridge (a) deck, (b) external prestressed.

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

2. Hütten Bridge, Werthenstein, Lucerne (Switzerland) Project.

The "Hütten Bridge" was built in the 1950's and was designed for vehicles with a maximum total loading of 28 tons. The management of the surrounding forests nowadays required the bridge to carry heavier loads of timber with larger trucks taking up to 40 tons. Neither of the two main bridge beams on the three-span bridge could undertake this new loading (Figure 3a) and they both had to be strengthened for the increased flexural and shear force loadings. Both beams were strengthened with prestressed Sika® CarboDur® CFRP plates up to 30 metres long on both sides. The end anchorage of the prestressed plates consisted of continuous shear connectors through the beams (Figure 3b), which introduced the tensioning forces into the beam. SikaWrap® fabric loops were used for the shear strengthening. Slots were first cut vertically in the deck slab so that the loops could completely surround both the tension and compression zones of the beams. The loops were then inserted in several layers and bonded together with Sikadur® Adhesive.

Figure 3. Hütten Bridge (a) deck, (b) external prestress.

3. Sung San Bridge, Seoul (Korea) Project

The "Sung San bridge" is a reinforced concrete multispan two-way bridge in the City of Seoul, South Korea, with a total length of 120 meters (8x15 m) and a width of 17 meters. The deck slab on the bridge had large transverse cracks in several places (Figure 4a). They were as a consequence of ever increasing traffic loads for which the longitudinal reinforcement in the deck slab had not been designed. Strengthening of the tensile resistance underneath was particularly necessary around the abutments and supports. In some cases the end anchorages also had to be located directly in the supports, i.e. in the haunch. Sika Solution The longitudinal strengthening was achieved with prestressed Sika® CarboDur® CFRP plates. The plates were deflected around the haunches by a steel saddle to prevent the plates becoming attached (Figure 4b). The end anchorage of the CFRP plate could then be transferred directly to the sloping part of the haunch.

Figure 4. Sung San Bridge (a) deck, (b) external prestressed plates.

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

4. Clinton & Hopkins Bridges, Ohio (USA) Project.

Both of these 6 span bridges are of precast box girder construction, which were precast by the prestressing bed method and then jointed on site. They are 155m and 131m in length respectively (Figure 5a). Leaking drains and a defective drainage system caused corrosion damage to the prestressing wires, requiring the box girders to be strengthened. The precast box girders had been designed to be very slender and therefore in the end anchorage zones, the concrete was also strengthened locally with SikaWrap® fabrics. The prestressed Sika® CarboDur® CFRP plates (Figure 5b) supplemented the main damaged tensile reinforcement and restored the structural strength and integrity of the bridges.

(a) (b)
Figure 5. U (a) deck, (b) external prestressed.

5. A7 Bridge Viaduct, Zaandijk (Netherlands) Project.

The "A7" is the main motorway connection between the city of Amsterdam and the northern provinces of Friesland and Groningen. The viaduct is located near Zaandijk, some 10 km north of Amsterdam. The two-span viaduct is constructed with a prestressed concrete deck supported by 2 transverse beams in the middle section and another beam at each end. Columns support the beams (Figure 6a). During routine maintenance work, one of the pre-tensioning cables at the edge of the west part of the viaduct (traffic direction north to south) was severely damaged. The cable was touched by the drilling equipment for a new rain water drain (Figure 6b). The extent of the damage was difficult to assess, but the Rijkswaterstaat (Dutch Ministry of Transport) estimated a potential loss of approximately 50% of pre-tensioning capacity. The viaduct was therefore closed to traffic above 28 tons in the southerly direction. Heavy traffic was then forced to go the longer way around via Zaandijk.

(a) (b)
Figure 6. A7 Bridge Viaduct (a) deck, (b) external prestressed.

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

6. Auckland's Iconic Grafton Bridge.

was the world's largest single span reinforced concrete arch bridge when originally built in 1910. Today it is recognized as one of the 100 most significant concrete structures in the world (Figure 7a). It has continued its history of innovation, by using Sika CarboShear technology for structural strengthening works that were required in 2010. Sika CarboDur® CFRP plates were installed on the underside of the reinforced concrete beams to provide additional mid-span movement resistance (Figure 7b). The Sika CarboShear L shaped CFRP profiles were then installed, in pairs, around the beams and up into the deck slab to improve the shear performance. Almost 100 years after the bridge was built, this bridge strengthening was part of the 'Auckland Central Connector' project. This has provided the landmark structure with essential seismic resistance to modern standards, enabling it to withstand a one-in-1000-year earthquake, as well as increased capacity to carry higher volumes of bus traffic and to accommodate a possible future light rail transport system – all without altering the bridge's appearance or changing its heritage status. Sika CarboDur® strips and CarboShear L plates bonded to the concrete structure (Figure 7c). The overall refurbishment work included: i) strengthening the bridge columns using additional steel reinforcement, ii) strengthening the bridge beams with Sika CarboDur® CFRP plates and Sika CarboShear L profiles, iii) installing new, reinforced-concrete shear keys and deck links to resist horizontal seismic forces, iv) removing green growth and repairing cracks in the original concrete, v) replacing the deck joints and bridge bearings

Figure 7. Auckland's Iconic Grafton Bridge (a) deck, (b) external bonded CFRPs and (c) strips and L shaped plates.

7. The Sunshine Skyway Bridge, Tampa Bay, Florida, Usa

The Sunshine Skyway Bridge (Figure 8) is one of the most widely recognized landmark structures in the USA. With its signature bright yellow stay cables, the bridge design resembles a sailboat, with its towers holding up the triangular sails across Tampa Bay. During routine inspections, an increase in shear cracking was observed, mainly on the exterior trestle span girders. The structure needed to be repaired and protected, not only to retain its strength and shear requirements, but also to withstand the aggressive marine environment. In addition to the repairs by crack injection and damaged concrete replacement, the bridge also needed to be structurally strengthened to carry additional loads. Due to its many advantages over steel and other methods, the SikaWrap® fabric strengthening system was chosen to strengthen the girders. A bi-directional SikaWrap® fabric was installed in several layers around the girders, and the effectiveness of this approach was also confirmed by a full scale test prior to the installation. The resin impregnated fabric and exposed concrete surfaces were then covered and protected with a water-dispersed acrylic coating. By detailed planning of the works and using well trained specialists experienced in working with these materials, the project was completed successfully and ahead of schedule. This refurbishment project also won the International Concrete Repair Institute (ICRI) 'Award of Excellence' in 2008.

Figure 8. The Sunshine Skyway Bridge.

8. The Pumarejo Bridge, Colombia.

Is one of the largest bridges in Colombia. Originally built in the early 1970's to allow development of the Northern Region of the country and to link Barranquilla City with the eastern side of the Magdalena River (Figure 9a), it was listed as one of the best concrete structures in the country by the Colombian Ready Mixed Concrete Association in 2006. However after three decades of exposure and service in this aggressive environment, the bridge was completely refurbished to repair areas of spalling concrete due to reinforcement corrosion (Figure 9b), and also areas eroded with the loss of coarse aggregates from the columns in and just above the river level. Pumarejo Bridge, Barran, Colombia International Concrete Repair Institute (ICRI): Sika won the ICRI Award of Merit in the Strengthening Category in 2009. Click on the QR Code to learn more about Sika's ICRI Award-Winning Projects. The refurbishment was undertaken in several stages in 2006 and 2008, and it was also decided to strengthen it in 2011. The repair works included removal of weak concrete, cleaning and protection of exposed steel reinforcement, concrete replacement with SikaTop® and EpoCem® systems after crack injection, steel jacketing around the columns, plus overall protection with an impregnating corrosion inhibitor and a protective coating. Sika products and systems were selected and used exclusively for all of this repair and refurbishment work. This project won the International Concrete Repair Institute (ICRI) 'Award of Merit' in 2009. Few years after the initial concrete repair works were completed shear cracks were noticed in the beams and the requirement for structural strengthening was decided by the Engineers. After sealing and filling the cracks with Sikadur® injection resin, the substrate was prepared and a lightweight SikaWrap® fabric strengthening system was applied in two directions and finally the areas were covered with a SikaTop® coating (Figure 9c). This full-scale refurbishment and upgrading with Sika products and systems has given this engineering icon a new future. The Pumarejo Bridge will now be able to handle the anticipated rising traffic volumes, increased loads and environmental exposure for years to come, requiring only routine maintenance in the coming years.

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

Figure 9. Pumarejo Bridge (a) deck, (b) repairing spalling concrete and (c) fabric applied.

9. A34 Pont Du Dancourt, Ardennes, France.

The Pont du Dancourt is a composite steel and concrete bridge, located on the A34 Motorway in the Ardennes in Northern France. It was originally built in 1972 and is part of the National AutoRoute System. Approximately 28.000 vehicles cross the 140 m long, 3-span bridge structure every day and more than 20% of them are heavy trucks. Each carriageway of the bridge consists of 5 steel beams on reinforced concrete piers that support a reinforced concrete deck. A routine inspection and assessment of the bridge highlighted corrosion on the structure, plus potential damage from fatigue and insufficient flexural strength for the traffic loads (Figure 10a). To correct the deficiencies outlined in the assessment, the structure was strengthened with an externally applied Sika CarboDur® system. After the steel substrate was cleaned and prepared by abrasive blast cleaning, the prefabricated CarboDur® CFRP plates were then immediately bonded to the steel surface with Sikadur® structural adhesive (Figure 10b). With these strengthening measures, the mechanical characteristics of the structure were increased and the amplitudes of stresses due to movement were reduced; thus the service life of the bridge was significantly extended. This was the first experience in France of strengthening this type of structure with bonded CFRP.

(a) (b)

Figure 10. Pont Du Dancourt (a) deck, (b) CFRP plates.

10. Penang Bridge, Malaysia

There are two connecting the Malaysian mainland with the Penang peninsula. The original Penang Bridge is a dual carriageway toll bridge that spans 13.5 km and was completed and first opened to traffic

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

in 1985, and by 2010 was used by over 80.000 vehicles a day (Figure 11a). Following an accidental fire in 2010, a complete inspection and structural assessment of the bridge was undertaken. In addition to the concrete repairs that were necessary after the fire and 25 years exposure in the aggressive marine environment, the structure was also found to be in need of structural strengthening to replace the damaged steel tendons. The damaged concrete was removed and the reinforced concrete beams were repaired with a SikaTop® concrete repair System and SikaGrout® poured concrete. The beams were then strengthened to the performance levels required by the Penang Bridge, Penang Island, Malaysia Engineers, using a layered build-up of the Sika CarboDur® CFRP System (Figure 11b). Finally, all of the exposed concrete and CarboDur® plate surfaces were given a protective Sikagard® coating to protect them against UV light and future attack from the aggressive marine environment respectively. The Second Penang Bridge was completed in 2014 and at 24 km, is the longest bridge in South-East Asia and designed to last for 120 years with minimal maintenance. Sika's involvement started at the very beginning with systems for the concreting and construction work, from curing compounds to Sikadur® structural resins and concrete protection with Sikagard® hydrophobic impregnation, all contributing significantly to the required durability of the structure.

(a) (b)
Figure 11. 10. Penang Bridge (a) deck, (b) CFRP plates.

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

Appendix A

Table A.1: Measurands, techniques and principles in SHFM of infrastructure assets and use in risk & resilience assessments

no	measurands	structural health and functionality monitoring (SHFM) techniques	type	function principle	assessment of risk & resilience	
					directly	indirectly
1.	displacement/deformations/	linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) 3-D laser scanning digital image correlation (DIC) fibre optic-based sensors global positioning system (GPS)	I I, A, T C, D, WL, I, A I, WL, C, D, AU, A, U	change of the magnetic flux triangulation matching reference-deformed image internal reflection of light -guided wave triangulation	SHM damage deterioration vulnerability	robustness; idle time; restoration time; rapidity; loss; functionality
2.	acceleration	accelerometer (e.g. piezoelectric, capacitive, force balanced) micro-electro-mechanical sensors (MEMS) string pots (linear potentiometer)	I I I	mechanical motion of the mass in spring electrostatic actuation rotor electromotive force (internal resistance)	SHM changes in geometry, stiffness deterioration vulnerability	robustness idle time restoration time
3.	strain	electrical resistance strain gauges vibrating wire gauge sensors fiber optic-based sensors interferometry digital image correlation (DIC) electrochemical/electromechanical fatigue sensors	I I I I C, D, WL, I A	electrical resistance internal reflection of light (guided wave) superposition of waves (light or electromagnetic) matching reference-deformed image electrochemical reaction: electrolyte/ conductors/ electric current	SHM changes deterioration vulnerability	robustness idle time restoration time rapidity
4.	forces	load cells (e.g. hydraulic, pneumatic, piezoelectric) fibre optic-based sensors	I I, D	electrical resistance internal reflection of light (guided wave)	SHM vulnerability	redundancy robustness
5.	load	lorry/ vehicles	I, T	suspensions	SHM vulnerability	

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

	chlorides/ air/water pollution wind thunders	moisture/chloride/ air/water pollution content sensors/ hygrometers/ anemometers		risk PDF	restoration time
10.	traffic	cameras satellites drones network of stations crowd data (open access)	I, C, D, AU, U I, C, D, WL, AU, U, A I, C, D, WL, AU, U, A	optical configuration FM functionality risk idle time restoration time	PDF
11.	accumulation of snow/ water/ debris	cameras satellites drones network of stations crowd data (open access)	I, C, D, AU, U I, C, D, WL, AU, U, A I, C, D, WL, AU, U, A	FM risk idle time restoration time	PDF vulnerability

type: Contactless (C), Distant (D), Wireless (WL), Instrumented (I), Autonomous (AU), Unattended (U), Aerial (A), Terrestrial (T)

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

Table A.2: List of the advantages and disadvantages of non-destructive testing (NDT) and monitoring techniques

no	structural health and functionality monitoring (SHFM) techniques	advantages	disadvantages	cost including resources	assessment of risk & resilience
1.	visual inspections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • rapid • inexpensive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • only accessible areas • superficial damages only • time-consuming to evaluate results • experienced surveyor needed • requires special instrumentation (e.g. magnifier) 	low	damage deterioration structural modifications vulnerability functionality obstructions
2.	coin tap test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • no training or specialisation equipment needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • low accuracy • subjective • experienced surveyor needed 	low	deterioration
3.	chain dragging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • easy to apply 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • subjective and dependent on the inspector's experience • disruption of function 	low	deterioration
4.	laser scanning systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • precision • global survey and point cloud of the asset 	reduced accuracy due to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • climatic conditions • distance from the asset • different materials and surfaces • measures the different orientation of the structure 	moderate	structural changes deterioration vulnerability
5.	accelerometers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • time history of response • durable over time • little dependency on the traffic loads 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • errors due to numerical integration • large amount of data • intensive post-processing • amplification is needed 	moderate	damage structural changes deterioration vulnerability redundancy
6.	fiber optics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • measures two points in one time and the distributed configuration • multiple measurements • diverse types of measurements (e.g. temperature, strains, stresses) • wide dynamic range • immune to electromagnetic interference • dependent on different techniques & principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sensitive to thermal difference/temperature • sensitivity in installation • challenging to decompose wavelengths of different measurements 	moderate	structural changes deterioration vulnerability

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

(Antunes et al. 2012)					
7.	laser station	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> measures nodes coordinates conversion to coordinates speed of measurement capturing data related to distance (range), intensity, and colour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> no dynamic measurements accuracy depends on the stability of the station 	high	changes in positions deterioration risk PDF
8.	Acoustic emission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> real-time & continuous monitoring long-distance local & global monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> requires experienced surveyors limited measurements in one test real-time noise difficulty in quantification of results needs amplification of results; post-processing difficulties to convert waveforms into useful data need for many sensors 	moderate-high	deterioration vulnerability
9.	digital image correlation (DIC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> simple to use noncontact remote sensing one picture even for large areas accuracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> needs accuracy in position and alignment of images needs penetrant or colour stability of camera and lens quality affect results (Hoult et al. 2016) weather conditions affect accuracy (e.g. humidity, wind) accuracy due to shape of correlation 	moderate	changes deterioration vulnerability restoration
10.	Concrete resistivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> one measurement at the rebar detects corrosion 	influence due to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> concrete mix initial chloride concentration environmental exposure lower accuracy within a small area 	low	deterioration vulnerability
11.	electrochemical impedance spectroscopy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ideal for corrosion detection detection of microplasticity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> application on specific locations damage detection, but not localisation difficult to choose appropriate equivalent circuit 	low	deterioration vulnerability
12.	electrical resistance strain gauges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> measures principal stresses different angles of measurement at the same time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high noise level due to exposure to environmental conditions 	low	deterioration vulnerability

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • post-processing to remove noise 		
13.	long gauge fiber optics (interferometry)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • capable of measuring in-plane and out-of-plane motion in 3D • high precision • dynamic range • fatigue cracking detection • not affected by soil-structure interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sophisticated equipment required • high-resolution capacity 	high	deterioration vulnerability
14.	electrical resistance load cells	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • small scale • many different types, e.g. tension/compression, miniature, strain, beam, platform, canister style 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • influence due to surrounding magnetic field or local materials • (metals/ concrete reinforcement) • needs measurements of switching field in both directions 	low	deterioration vulnerability
15.	piezoelectric load cells	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thin, light and flexible • customized • low power needed (electrical field) • can be wireless 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • calibrated by user • less accurate • affected by environmental conditions 	low	deterioration vulnerability
16.	global positioning system (GPS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dynamic monitoring of displacements • real-time monitoring generation of a datum/ reference model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • limited measurements due to obstacles, e.g. tunnels • improving the precision of measurements increases the cost • not suitable for low-frequency structures 	moderate	deterioration vulnerability functionality idle time PDF
17.	ground-penetrating radar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fast data acquisition • large amount of information • no coupling medium is required; covers a large testing area 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-measuring technique (imaging device) • interpretation of results is challenging- low resolution 	moderate- high	structural modifications deterioration vulnerability
18.	impact echo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • used for damage characterisation (mapping and type of damages) • reliable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • many test points required • affected by the complexity of the structure • accuracy in inclination of sensors in one-sided test 	moderate- high	deterioration vulnerability
19.	infrared thermography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • easy to interpret • radiation used is not harmful to health • minimal traffic delay • two-dimensional thermal images 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • needs specialised software • influence on the radiation due to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ differences between surfaces or debris presence ○ weather conditions e.g. wind, temperature 	moderate- high	deterioration vulnerability PDF risk functionality

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

			○ water presence		
20.	Linear Polarization Resistance (LPR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> warning for corrosion rate increase localised corrosion detection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> low precision polarisation needed 	low	deterioration vulnerability
21.	Micro-Electro-Mechanical Sensors (MEMS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> miniaturisation of the sensors multiple systems in one chip reduced cost low to zero power need detection of fatigue cycles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> influence of the thermal drift high signal-to-noise ratio 	low	deterioration vulnerability functionality PDF
22.	linear potentiometer (string pots)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inexpensive large measurement range 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> deterioration sensitivity 	low	deterioration vulnerability
23.	Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> direct measurement accuracy functions at low temperatures with accuracy high sensitivity and resolution wide range of applications low hysteresis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> limited temperature operation range affected by changes of temperature affected by magnetic fields voltage distortion in the output 	low	deterioration vulnerability
24.	microcell corrosion rate sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> monitor corrosion depth by using arrays of anodes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> accuracy is limited 	low	deterioration vulnerability PDF
25.	potential measurements of chloride content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> surface measurements possible to create contour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> influence of humidity corrosion dependent dependent on the resistivity of concrete at the reinforcement 	low	deterioration vulnerability PDF
26.	electrical resistance thermometers Thermocouples Thermistors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> no power supply required cost-effective simple to use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> requires reference temperature not linear measurement of changes low stability limited temperature range 	low	deterioration vulnerability risk idle time functionality PDF
27.	Electrochemical/mechanical impedance spectroscopy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> wide frequency range validity of data detection of minute changes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high-resistance materials affected by porosity complex data analysis 	high	deterioration vulnerability PDF risk
28.	scour detection devices (single-use/ pulse or radar / buried or driven rod systems/ sound-wave devices/ fiber-Bragg grating/ electrical conductivity devices, GPR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> simple reliable estimation of scour depth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> single-use finite amount of stored power long probes/ manual operation temperature affects measurements not suitable for continuous monitoring sensitivity to vibrations 	high	deterioration vulnerability PDF risk

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • limitations due to heavy flood • use of mercury - risk for contamination of the environment 		
29.	tiltmeters/ inclinometers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • accuracy in measurements • static and dynamic measurements • total stations of multiple measurements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • point measurement (not relative) • numerous measurements needed • affected by temperature, mechanical stress • impractical for long-term use • poor durability 	low	deterioration vulnerability risk idle time functionality PDF
30.	ultrasonic C-scan imaging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • detects both corrosion and voids in a single test damage characterisation and mapping technique 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the interpretation of data is challenging 	moderate	deterioration vulnerability robustness
31.	vibrating wire strain gauges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • accurate measurements over time • immune to electromagnetic interference • superior durability • easy installation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • need to account for gauge factor for accuracy • influence of temperature-unequal strains in the medium 	low	deterioration vulnerability robustness
32.	moisture/ chloride/ air pollution content sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • simple use • anything else? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • affected by structure age • affected by crack width under immersion 	low	deterioration vulnerability PDF risk
33.	unmanned airborne visual inspections- measurements-data collection (drones/ cameras/ satellite images)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • distant measurements • applications in inaccessible sites, e.g. after a disaster • cost-efficiency • continuous measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • accuracy • human guidance 	moderate	deterioration vulnerability PDF risk functionality idle time

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

References:

- [1] Saviotti, A. Bridge Assessment, Management & Life Cycle Analysis. *J. Mod. Appl. Sci.* 2014, 8, 167–183.
- [2] Omar, T., & Nehdi, M. L. (2018). Condition assessment of reinforced concrete bridges: Current practice and research challenges. *Infrastructures*, 3(3), 36.
- [3] Agdas, D., Rice, J. A., Martinez, J. R., & Lasa, I. R. (2016). Comparison of visual inspection and structural-health monitoring as bridge condition assessment methods. *Journal of Performance of Constructed Facilities*, 30(3), 04015049.
- [4] AASHTO. (2011) Manual for Bridge Evaluation, 2nd ed.; AASHTO: Washington, DC, USA.
- [5] Zanini, M. A., Faleschini, F., & Casas, J. R. (2019). State-of-research on performance indicators for bridge quality control and management. *Frontiers in Built Environment*, 5, 22.
- [6] Scott, M., Rezaizadeh, A., Delahaza, A., Santos, C., Moore, M., Graybeal, B. and Washer, G. (2003). A comparison of non-destructive evaluation methods for bridge deck assessment. *NDT & E International*, 36(4), pp.245-255.
- [7] ASTM D 4580-86, Annual book of ASTM standards (1992), Standard practice for measuring delaminations in concrete bridge decks by sounding, American Standards for Testing Materials, 1992.
- [8] Fujino, Y., Siringoringo, D.M., Ikeda, Y., Nagayama, T. and Mizutani, T., 2019. Research and Implementations of Structural Monitoring for Bridges and Buildings in Japan. *Engineering*, 5(6), 1093-1119.
- [9] McCann, D. and Forde, M. (2001). Review of NDT methods in the assessment of concrete and masonry structures. *NDT & E International*, 34(2), pp.71-84.
- [10] Gastineau A., Johnson T. and Schultz A., (2009) Bridge Health Monitoring and Inspections Systems -A Survey of Methods, Technical Report, Department of Civil Engineering University of Minnesota, Minnesota Department of Transportation.
- [11] SHM: Structural Health Monitoring. (2013). A Major Qualifying Project Report Submitted to the Faculty Of the WORCESTER POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE.
- [12] Yang, D.Y., Frangopol, D.M., 2019. Life-cycle management of deteriorating civil infrastructure considering resilience to lifetime hazards: A general approach based on renewal-reward processes. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 183, 197-212.
- [13] FEMA: Federal Emergency Management Agency (US) (Ed.). (2017). Rapid visual screening of buildings for potential seismic hazards: A handbook. Government Printing Office.
- [14] Karabinis A.I.; Rousakis T.C. (2010). Evaluation of RVS method for pre-seismic assessment of structures utilizing post-earthquake damage investigations, in Mazzolani FM, editor. *Urban Habitat Constructions Under Catastrophic Events: Proceedings of the COST C26 Action Final Conference*. CRC Press; 2010 Aug 27.
- [15] Eschmann, C., & Wundsam, T. (2017). Web-based georeferenced 3D inspection and monitoring of bridges with unmanned aircraft systems. *Journal of Surveying Engineering*, 143(3), 04017003.
- [16] Greenwood, W. W., Lynch, J. P., & Zekkos, D. (2019). Applications of UAVs in civil infrastructure. *Journal of Infrastructure Systems*, 25(2), 04019002.
- [17] Gkoumas, K., Marques Dos Santos, F. L., van Balen, M., Tsakalidis, A., Ortega Hortelano, A., Grosso, M., & Pekár, F. (2019). Research and Innovation in Bridge Maintenance, Inspection and Monitoring (No. JRC115319).
- [18] Ganin, A. A., Mersky, A. C., Jin, A. S., Kitsak, M., Keisler, J. M., & Linkov, I. (2019). Resilience in intelligent transportation systems (ITS). *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 100, 318-329.
- [19] Ko, J. and Ni, Y. (2005). Technology developments in structural health monitoring of large-scale bridges. *Engineering Structures*, 27(12), pp.1715-1725.
- [20] Xu, Y. (2012). *Structural health monitoring of long-span suspension bridges*. London and New York: CRC Press.
- [21] Skarżyński, Ł., & Suchorzewski, J. (2018). Mechanical and fracture properties of concrete reinforced with recycled and industrial steel fibers using Digital Image Correlation technique and X-ray micro computed tomography. *Construction and Building Materials*, 183, 283-299.
- [22] Hoult, N., Dutton, M., Hoag, A. and Take, W. (2016). Measuring Crack Movement in Reinforced Concrete Using Digital Image Correlation: Overview and Application to Shear Slip Measurements. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 104(8), pp.1561-1574.
- [23] Palacz, M., 2018. Spectral Methods for Modelling of Wave Propagation in Structures in Terms of Damage Detection— A Review. *Applied Sciences*, 8(7), p.1124.
- [24] Ou, Y.W., Dertimanis, V.K. and Chatzi, E.N., (2017). Operational Damage Localization of Wind Turbine Blades. In *International Conference on Experimental Vibration Analysis for Civil Engineering Structures* (pp. 261-272). Springer, Cham.
- [25] Achillopoulou, D.V. and Pau, A., 2017. Characterization of defects in plates using shear and Lamb waves. *Procedia Engineering*, 199, pp.2001-2007.
- [26] Pau, A., Achillopoulou, D.V. and Vestroni, F., 2016. Scattering of guided shear waves in plates with discontinuities. *NDT & E International*, 84, pp.67-75.
- [27] Chatzi, E.N. and Spiridonakos, M.D., 2015. Structural identification and monitoring based on uncertain/limited information. In *MATEC Web of Conferences* (Vol. 24, p. 01003). EDP Sciences.
- [28] Pavlopoulou, S., Staszewski, W.J. and Soutis, C., 2013. Evaluation of instantaneous characteristics of guided ultrasonic waves for structural quality and health monitoring. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 20(6), pp.937-955.
- [29] Xu, B., Giurgiutiu, V. and Yu, L., 2009, March. Lamb waves decomposition and mode identification using matching pursuit method. In *Sensors and Smart Structures Technologies for Civil, Mechanical, and Aerospace Systems 2009* (Vol. 7292, p. 72920I). International Society for Optics and Photonics.
- [30] Rose, J.L., 2004. Ultrasonic guided waves in structural health monitoring. In *Key Engineering Materials* (Vol. 270, pp. 14-21). Trans Tech Publications.

D5: Report on real case studies: assessment, monitoring, strengthening measures.

- [31] Fujino, Y., Siringoringo, D.M., Ikeda, Y., Nagayama, T. and Mizutani, T., 2019. Research and Implementations of Structural Monitoring for Bridges and Buildings in Japan. *Engineering*, 5(6), 1093-1119.
- [32] Fujino, Y. and Siringoringo, D. 2011. Bridge monitoring in Japan: the needs and strategies. *Structure and Infrastructure Engineering*, 7(7-8), pp.597-611.
- [33] Lloyd's Register foundation, (2014). Foresight review of big data: Towards data-centric engineering, Report Series: No.2014.2 <https://www.lrfoundation.org.uk/en/publications/foresight-review-of-big-data/> (accessed online, March 2020).
- [34] <https://infrawatch.liacs.nl/> (accessed online July 2021).
- [35] Chen, H. P. (2018). Structural health monitoring of large civil engineering structures. John Wiley & Sons.
- [36] Simpson, T., Dertimanis, V., Papadimitriou, C., & Chatzi, E. (2019). On the Potential of Dynamic Sub-structuring Methods for Model Updating. *Structural Health Monitoring* 2019.
- [37] Abdeljaber, O., Avci, O., Kiranyaz, S., Gabbouj, M., & Inman, D. J. 2017. Real-time vibration-based structural damage detection using one-dimensional convolutional neural networks. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 388, 154-170.
- [38] Friswell, M., & Mottershead, J. E. 2013. Finite element model updating in structural dynamics (Vol. 38). Springer Science & Business Media.
- [39] Jaishi, B., & Ren, W. X. (2006). Damage detection by finite element model updating using modal flexibility residual. *Journal of sound and vibration*, 290(1-2), 369-387.
- [40] Teughels, A., Maeck, J., & De Roeck, G. (2002). Damage assessment by FE model updating using damage functions. *Computers & structures*, 80(25), 1869-1879.
- [41] Bruns, M., Hofmeister, B., Griebmann, T., & Rolfes, R. 2019. Comparative study of parameterizations for damage localization with finite element model updating.
- [42] Wang, W., Mottershead, J. E., Ihle, A., Siebert, T., & Schubach, H. R. (2011). Finite element model updating from full-field vibration measurement using digital image correlation. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 330(8), 1599-1620.
- [43] Pedram, M., Esfandiari, A., & Khedmati, M. R. (2016). Finite element model updating using strain-based power spectral density for damage detection. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 23(11), 1314-1333.
- [44] Wang, Y., Zhu, X., Hao, H., & Ou, J. (2011). Spectral element model updating for damage identification using clonal selection algorithm. *Advances in Structural Engineering*, 14(5), 837-856.
- [45] Chkrebti, O. A., Campbell, D. A., Calderhead, B., & Girolami, M. A. (2016). Bayesian solution uncertainty quantification for differential equations. *Bayesian Analysis*, 11(4), 1239-1267.
- [46] Mottershead, J. E., Link, M., & Friswell, M. I. (2011). The sensitivity method in finite element model updating: a tutorial. *Mechanical systems and signal processing*, 25(7), 2275-2296.
- [47] Weng, S., Xia, Y., Xu, Y. L., & Zhu, H. P. (2011). Substructure based approach to finite element model updating. *Computers & structures*, 89(9-10), 772-782.
- [48] Neftci, E. O., Mostafa, H., & Zenke, F. (2019). Surrogate gradient learning in spiking neural networks: Bringing the power of gradient-based optimization to spiking neural networks. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 36(6), 51-63.
- [49] Alkayem, N. F., Cao, M., Zhang, Y., Bayat, M., & Su, Z. 2018. Structural damage detection using finite element model updating with evolutionary algorithms: a survey. *Neural computing and applications*, 30(2), 389-411.
- [50] Wang, Y and Zhang, T (2013) Finite element model updating using estimation of distribution algorithm In: SHMII-6 2013: The 6th International Conference on Structural Health Monitoring of Intelligent Infrastructure, 2013-12-09 - 2013-12-09, Hong Kong, China.
- [51] Zhang, T., Biswal, S., & Wang, Y. (2019). SHMnet: Condition assessment of bolted connection with beyond human-level performance. *Structural Health Monitoring*, 1475921719881237.
- [52] https://gbr.sika.com/content/dam/dms/gb01/2/Refurbishment_Structural%20Strengthening%20-%20Case%20Studies%20for%20web.pdf (accessed online July 2021).